

Sultanate of Oman

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Director of Antiquities

سلطنة عمان

وزارة الاعلام والسياحة

ص.ب ٦٠٠ ، تلفون ٢٣٢١

برقيا: الاعلام التلكس ام بي ٢٦٥

مسقط

Ref :

الاشارة :

Date: 12.3.1974

التاريخ :

Dr. W. Sumner,
Ohio State University,
65, South Oval Drive,
Columbus,
Ohio.

Dear Bill,

I hope everything goes well with the family. I enclose copies of my latest academic offerings - I assume you already have the Sasanian maritime trade I did with Dave Whitehouse. The others are much in the same series.

I have recently been looking at my material on the Marv Dasht Sasanian and Islamic sites. Do you have figures on the areas of all these sites? If you do I'd be very glad to see them.

Best wishes

Andrew

Andrew Williamson